

The Psalm Project

Discovering the Spiritual World through the Psalms

Psalm 66

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The Goal of this project:

This research project will examine the 150 psalms for the spiritual awareness each Psalm offers. Each Psalm will be examined by its language and the commentary of the Sages. The spiritual awareness analysis will be done in alignment with Ari's definition of the Tree of life, the Book of Creation, and the Zohar. Each Verse of the Psalm will be rewritten using the intent of the language and spiritual commentary to convey its spiritual lesson.

The Main Resources:

The Zohar

The Book of Creation

Ari's writing on the Tree of Life and the Ten Sefirot

The Theological Wordbook of the Old Testament

Samson Hirsch's commentary on the Psalms

Tehillim – Psalms – A new translation with a commentary anthologized from the Talmudic and rabbinic sources

Accordance Bible Software

Psalm 66

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>Psa. 66:0 For the choir director. A Song. A Psalm.</p>	<p>Psa. 66:1 לְמִנְצֵחַ שִׁיר מִזְמוֹר</p>
<p>Psa. 66:1 “Shout joyfully to God, all the earth; ² Sing the ^aglory of His name; Make His ^bpraise glorious. ³ Say to God, “How ^aawesome are Your works! Because of the greatness of Your power Your enemies will ^{1b}give feigned obedience to You. ⁴ ““All the earth will worship You, And will ^bsing praises to You; They will sing praises to Your name.” ¹Selah.</p>	<p>הָרִיעוּ לְאֱלֹהִים כָּל־הָאָרֶץ : ² זַמְּרוּ כְבוֹד־שְׁמוֹ שִׁימוּ כְּבוֹד תְּהַלְתּוּ : ³ אַמְרוּ לְאֱלֹהִים מַה־נּוֹרָא מֵעֲשִׂיךָ בְּרַב עֲזֶיךָ יִכְתְּשׁוּ לָךְ אֵיבֶיךָ : ⁴ כָּל־הָאָרֶץ יִשְׁתַּחֲוּוּ לָךְ וַיִּזְמְרוּ לָךְ יִזְמְרוּ שִׁמְךָ סֵלָה : ⁵ לְכוּ וּרְאוּ מַפְעֵלוֹת אֱלֹהִים נּוֹרָא עָלֶיךָ עַל־בְּנֵי אָדָם : ⁶</p>
<p>Psa. 66:5 “Come and see the works of God, <i>Who is ^bawesome in His deeds toward the sons of men.</i> ⁶ He ^aturned the sea into dry land; They passed through ^bthe river on foot; There let us ^crejoice in Him! ⁷ He ^arules by His might forever; His ^beyes keep watch on the nations; Let not the rebellious ^cexalt themselves. Selah.</p>	<p>וּרְאוּ מַפְעֵלוֹת אֱלֹהִים נּוֹרָא עָלֶיךָ עַל־בְּנֵי אָדָם : ⁶ תִּפְךָ יָם לְיַבֶּשֶׁת בְּנָהָר יַעֲבִרוּ בְּרַגְלֵי שָׁם נִשְׁמַחְתָּה בּוֹ : ⁷ מִשֵּׁל בְּגִבוּרָתוֹ אֵעוֹלָם עֵינָיו בְּגוֹיִם תִּצְפִּינָה תְּסוֹדְרִים אֶל־יָרִימוּ [יָרוּמוּ] לָמוּ סֵלָה : ⁸ בְּרָכוּ עַמִּים אֱלֹהֵינוּ יְהִשְׁמִיעוּ קוֹל תְּהַלְתּוּ : ⁹ תִּשְׁמַע גַּבְשִׁינוּ בְּתַיִים וְלֹא־נָתַן לַמּוֹט</p>
<p>Psa. 66:8 Bless our God, O peoples, And ^{1a}sound His praise abroad, ⁹ Who ^{1a}keeps us in life And ^bdoes not allow our feet to ²slip.</p>	<p>בְּתַיִים וְלֹא־נָתַן לַמּוֹט</p>

¹⁰ For You have ^atried us, O God;
 You have ^brefined us as silver is refined.
¹¹ You ^abrought us into the net;
 You laid an oppressive burden upon our loins.
¹² You made men ^aride over our heads;
 We went through ^bfire and through water,
 Yet You ^bbrought us out into a place of abundance.
¹³ I shall ^acome into Your house with burnt offerings;
 I shall ^bpay You my vows,
¹⁴ Which my lips uttered
 And my mouth spoke when I was ^ain distress.
¹⁵ I shall ^aoffer to You burnt offerings of fat beasts,
 With the smoke of ^brams;
 I shall make *an offering of* ¹bulls with male goats. Selah.
Psa. 66:16 ^aCome *and* hear, all who ¹fear God,
 And I will ^btell of what He has done for my soul.
¹⁷ I cried to Him with my mouth,
 And ¹He was ^aextolled with my tongue.
¹⁸ If I ^{1a}regard wickedness in my heart,
 The ^bLord ²will not ³hear;
¹⁹ But certainly ^aGod has heard;
 He has given heed to the voice of my prayer.
²⁰ ^aBlessed be God,
 Who ^bhas not turned away my prayer
 Nor His lovingkindness from me.

רָגַלְנוּ : ¹⁰ כִּי־בַחֲנִיתָנוּ
 אֱלֹהִים צָרַפְתָּנוּ כַּצָּרָה־
 כֶּסֶף : ¹¹ הֵבֵאתָנוּ בַמְצוּרָה
 שָׁמַתָּ מוֹעֲקָה בְּמַתְנֵינוּ : ¹²
 הִרְכַּבְתָּ אֲנוֹשׁ לְרַאשֵׁינוּ
 בָּאנוּ־בָאֵשׁ וּבַמַּיִם וְהוֹצֵאתָנוּ
 לְרוֹיָה : ¹³ אָבוֹא בֵיתְךָ
 בְּעוֹלוֹת אֲשַׁלֵּם לְךָ נְדָרַי : ¹⁴
 אֲשֶׁר־פָּצוּ שְׂפִתַי וּדְבַר־פִּי
 בַצָּר־לִי : ¹⁵ עָלוֹת מִתַּיִם
 אֲעֹלָה־לְךָ עִם־קִטְוֹת
 אֵילִים אֲעֹשֶׂה בַקֶּרֶן עִם־
 עֲתוּדִים סֶלָה : ¹⁶ לְכוּ־שִׂמְעוּ
 וְאִסְפְּרָה כָל־יִרְאֵי אֱלֹהִים
 אֲשֶׁר עָשָׂה לְנַפְשִׁי : ¹⁷ אֲלֵיו
 פִּי־קָרָאתִי וְרוֹמָם תַּתַּת
 לְשׁוֹנִי : ¹⁸ אֲוֶן אִם־רָאִיתִי
 בְּלִבִּי לֹא יִשְׁמַע אֶלְנִי : ¹⁹
 אֲכֵן שָׁמַע אֱלֹהִים הַקְּשִׁיב
 בְּקוֹל תַּפְלְתִּי : ²⁰ בְּרוּךְ
 אֱלֹהִים אֲשֶׁר לֹא־הִסִּיר
 תַּפְלְתִּי וְחִסְדּוֹ מֵאֵתִי :

References

Psalm 66:1

^aPs 81:1; 95:1; 98:4; 100:1

Psalm 66:2

^aPs 79:9; Is 42:8

^bIs 42:12

Psalm 66:3

¹Lit *deceive*

^aPs 47:2; 65:5; 145:6

^bPs 18:44; 81:15

Psalm 66:4

¹*Selah* may mean: *Pause, Crescendo* or *Musical interlude*

^aPs 22:27; 67:7; 86:9; 117:1; Zech 14:16

^bPs 67:4

Psalm 66:5

^aPs 46:8

^bPs 106:22

Psalm 66:6

^aEx 14:21; Ps 106:9

^bJosh 3:16; Ps 114:3

^cPs 105:43

Psalm 66:7

^aPs 145:13

^bPs 11:4

^cPs 140:8

Psalm 66:8

¹Lit *cause to hear the sound of His praise*

^aPs 98:4

Psalm 66:9

¹Lit *puts our soul in life*

²Or *dotter, stumble*

^aPs 30:3

^bPs 121:3

Psalm 66:10

^aJob 23:10; Ps 7:9; 17:3; 26:2

^bIs 48:10; Zech 13:9; Mal 3:3; 1 Pet 1:7

Psalm 66:11

^aLam 1:13; Ezek 12:13

Psalm 66:12

^aIs 51:23

^bPs 78:21; Is 43:2

^cPs 18:19

Psalm 66:13

^aPs 96:8; Jer 17:26

^bPs 22:25; 116:14; Eccl 5:4

Psalm 66:14

^aPs 18:6

Psalm 66:15

¹Or *cattle*

^aPs 51:19

^bNum 6:14

Psalm 66:16

¹Or *revere*

^aPs 34:11

^bPs 71:15, 24

Psalm 66:17

¹Or *praise was under my tongue*

^aPs 30:1

Psalm 66:18

¹Or *had regarded*

²Or *would*

³Or *have heard*

^aJob 36:21; John 9:31

^bJob 27:9; Ps 18:41; Prov 1:28; 28:9; Is 1:15; James 4:3

Psalm 66:19

^aPs 18:6; 116:1, 2

Psalm 66:20

^aPs 68:35

^bPs 22:24

Targum

Psa. 66:1 For praise. A praise song. Shout for joy in the presence of the LORD, all inhabitants of the earth. ² Praise the glory of his name; set forth the glory of his praise. ³ Say in the presence of God, "How fearful are your works! For all the abundance of your works, your enemies will deny you." ⁴ All the inhabitants of the earth will bow down before you, and they will praise you, they will praise your name forever. ⁵ Come and see the works of God; fearful is the lord of destiny to the sons of men. ⁶ He turned the Red Sea to dry land; the sons of Israel crossed the river Jordan on their feet; he conveyed them to his holy mountain; there will we rejoice in his word. ⁷ He who rules over the world in the power of his strength, his eyes behold, the Gentiles; let the disobedient not exalt themselves forever. ⁸ Bless God, O Gentiles, and make the sound of his praise heard. ⁹ Who has designated our souls for the life of the age to come, and has not allowed our feet to be shaken. ¹⁰ For you have tried us, O God, you have refined us like a smith who refines silver. [ANOTHER TARGUM: For you have tried [us], for you have tested our fathers, O God; you exiled them among the kingdoms; you found them refined as one who purifies silver.] ¹¹ You brought us into the net, you placed chains on our loins. [ANOTHER TARGUM: You brought us into Egypt as into a net; you placed the rule of the Babylonians upon us, and we became like one on whose loins chains of trouble are placed.] ¹² You humbled us, you made our creditors ride over our heads; you judged us as if by fire and water, and you brought us out to a broad place. [ANOTHER TARGUM: The Medes and Greeks rode over us, they passed over our heads; you brought us among the Romans, who judge us like the cruel Chaldeans, who cast our father Abraham into the fiery furnace, and the Egyptians, who cast our infants into the water; yet you brought us up to freedom.] ¹³ I will enter your house with burnt-offerings, I will pay you my vows. [ANOTHER TARGUM: Just as you have mercy on us and redeem us, then we will enter your sanctuary with burnt-offerings and we will pay you our vows.] ¹⁴ Which opened my lips, and my mouth spoke, when I was in distress. ¹⁵ Fat burnt-offerings I will offer in your presence, with the sweet smell of the sacrifice of rams; I will make [sacrifice of] bulls with he-goats forever. ¹⁶ Come hear, and I will tell all who fear God what he has done for my soul. ¹⁷ I cried out to him with my mouth, and his praise was on my tongue. ¹⁸ If I saw falsehood in my heart, would the LORD not hear? ¹⁹ Truly, God has heard, he listened to the sound of my prayer. ²⁰ Blessed be God, who has not removed my prayer and his favor from me.

Spiritual Awareness

Introduction

David composed this Psalm near the end of his life. Now that peace existed in his kingdom he was free to dream of the Messianic future for his people. The first part of the Psalm deals with past events. Then the Psalm turns to the LORD's redemption of Israel.

Superscript and Verse one

David calls upon the world's nations to acknowledge the LORD's greatness through the manifestations that the LORD has done.

**To the Sefirah Netzach who grants victory, a song, a psalm. Waken
homage to God of all the Earth.**

Verse two

**Sing praises of the glory of His Name, and make all glorious things praise
His mighty acts.**

Verse three

David calls the reader's attention to the acts of the LORD on earth.

**Say unto God, What an awesome thing are your Acts, Your enemies feign
homage to You through the greatness of Your invincibility.**

Verse four

One day humanity will recognize the overpowering majesty of the LORD.

But all the earth shall bow down before You and sing Your praises; they shall sing praises to your name. Meditate on this Verse.

Verse five

The LORD demonstrated his Ways and His sovereignty throughout the history of Israel. By examining and learning about Israel, one can learn about how the LORD works in His creation.

Go and see the works of God; He is awesome in His acts above the sons of man.

Verse six

The event of the Red Sea is remembered because it demonstrated to Israel how much the LORD loves His people.

He has turned the sea into dry land; they passed through the river on foot; there we rejoiced in Him.

Verse seven

The idea of monotheism in David's day is seen in this verse.

Thus, He rules forever in His victorious might; His eyes look around among the nations; let not the disobedient exalt themselves. Meditate upon this verse.

Verse eight

David believed that the LORD was with him because of the victories and other prosperities that the nation enjoyed.

Bless our God, O peoples, and loudly proclaim the praise of His mighty acts.

Verse nine

David believed that the people of Israel were the immortal people among the nations. History proves that the LORD never allowed any nation to destroy Israel. Many have tried over the centuries.

That it is He Who has set up our soul in life and has not allowed our foot to be moved.

Verse ten

The LORD cleansed Israel in David's day.

For you, O God, have tried us; You have refined us even as silver is refined.

Verse eleven

בַּמְצוּדָה (bam'tzooda) means "net prey." This was Israel's political position in the world throughout history. They were a nation isolated from the rest of the world. The nation thought of itself as being captured in a cage.

You brought us into a cage; You imposed constraint upon our loins.

Verse twelve

The Hebrew says that the LORD caused men to ride over Israel in order to keep the people in line. Rabbi Hirsch says that these men were of the lowest class of men in the world. He used the word “rabble” to describe them. The people prayed to the LORD to stop the rabble. This verse could be a description of the Babylonian Exile.

You have caused the rabble to ride over our heads; we were forced to go through fire and water – and then You led us out into abundance.

Verses thirteen and fourteen

These two verses tell us that the Israelites in Babylon craved to go home. Upon returning to Jerusalem they wanted to enter the LORD’s home with offerings. Unfortunately, they would have to rebuild the LORD’s Temple. David had prophesized the Exile but not the destruction of the Temple. It would have been difficult for him to accept that the Temple where he was collecting building materials would one day be destroyed because of the sins of his descendants.

But I shall come into Your House with ascent-offerings; I will perform my vows unto You;

That which my lips have uttered and my mouth has spoken when distress was mine.

Verse fifteen

This verse is a more detailed description of what was brought as an ascent offering. This is the rule of Hillel. Many Christian interpreters would read this verse as parallel

to the preceding two. However, Hillel taught that what appears as a parallel verse expands the first.

I shall bring You ascent offerings of marrow-filled animals with the sweet smoke of rams; I will offer bullocks with goats. Meditate on this Verse.

Verse sixteen

Go and harken, all of you who fear God, so that I may tell what He has done for my soul.

Verse seventeen

This is the psalmist calling out for help from the LORD.

My mouth had cried unto Him, and exaltation was already beneath my tongue.

Verse eighteen, nineteen, and twenty

Had I discerned abuse in my heart, my Master would not have heard me.

But God has heard; He has attended to the voice of my prayer.

Blessed be God, Who has let neither my prayer nor His lovingkindness from the Sefirah Chesed depart from me.

Complete Psalm Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

To the Sefirah Netzach who grants victory, a song, a psalm. Waken homage to God of all the Earth.

Sing praises of the glory of His Name, and make all glorious things praise His mighty acts.

Say unto God, What an awesome thing are your Acts, Your enemies feign homage to You through the greatness of Your invincibility.

But all the earth shall bow down before You and sing Your praises; they shall sing praises to your name. Meditate on this verse.

Go and see the works of God; He is awesome in His acts above the sons of man.

He has turned the sea into dry land; they passed through the river on foot; there we rejoiced in Him.

Thus, He rules forever in His victorious might; His eyes look around among the nations; let not the disobedient exalt themselves. Meditate upon this verse.

Bless our God, O peoples, and loudly proclaim the praise of His mighty acts.

That it is He Who has set up our soul in life and has not allowed our foot to be moved.

For you, O God, have tried us; You have refined us even as silver is refined.

You brought us into a cage; You imposed constraint upon our loins.

You have caused the rabble to ride over our heads; we were forced to go through fire and water – and then You led us out into abundance.

But I shall come into Your House with ascent-offerings; I will perform my vows unto You;

That which my lips have uttered and my mouth has spoken when distress was mine.

I shall bring You ascent offerings of marrow-filled animals with the sweet smoke of rams; I will offer bullocks with goats. Meditate on this Verse.

Go and harken, all of you who fear God, so that I may tell what He has done for my soul.

My mouth had cried unto Him, and exaltation was already beneath my tongue.

Had I discerned abuse in my heart, my Master would not have heard me.

But God has heard; He has attended to the voice of my prayer.

Blessed be God, Who has let neither my prayer nor His lovingkindness from the Sefirah Chesed depart from me.

Appendix

Mystical Methodology to Prayer

All prayers result in spiritual energy which rises through the conduits that connect Sefirot realms. The "answer" to prayers is the transformation of spiritual energy from its original frequency to an appropriate frequency which will give the necessary results.

MHK V5 1/17/2016

Chambers of Aba and Ima of Briyah

Keter: prayers of thanksgiving come

MHK V1.1 6/23/14

